

EFFECT OF YOUTH EMPOWERMENT PROGRAMS ON YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT IN KADUNA SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF KADUNA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on empowerment programs on youth unemployment in Kaduna South LGA of Kaduna State, Nigeria. Unemployment is a major problem ravaging Nigeria's population today and youths are worst hit by it. In an attempt to harness the potentials of youths and address the problem of unemployment, Kaduna South LG in collaboration with Kaduna State government introduced skills acquisition programs to empower youths of the area. Against this backdrop, the study examined effect the programs on youths in terms of empowering them to be economically productive and be self-reliant. The study, a survey research generated its data through the conduct of interviews with coordinators of the programs and administration of questionnaires to beneficiaries. Data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions while Spearman rank correlation was used to test hypotheses. Results show that though a sizeable number of beneficiaries (youths) of the programs are now productively engaged and self-reliant as their income level have risen visibly and can now afford basic necessities of life to some extent. However, challenges of inadequate funding, shortage of qualified and experienced trainers and lack of soft loans were encountered. On this basis, the study recommends adequate budgetary provision, engagement of adequate qualified and experienced trainers, provision of soft loans and increased commitment of Kaduna South LG to ensure continuity.

Keywords: Empowerment; Kaduna South; Programs; Unemployment; Youth

INTRODUCTION

Youths are the future of every society as they constitute a larger chunk of the labour force and their energy and skills contribute in no small amount to societal development. Therefore, youths undoubtedly represent human capital that could propel a nation to a higher and enviable economic height in the comity of nations if efficiently employed and deployed in the task of nation building.

In spite of the enormous population of the country, estimated to be about 186 million people (United Nations, 2016) and its potentials, Nigeria has fared poorly in terms of development of its human capital especially her youth. Unemployment has been a major problem ravaging Nigeria's population today and the youth are mostly hit by it. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in its 2018 report puts the rate of unemployment at 23.1% with about 13.2 million youths unemployed. Youth unemployment reached an all-time high of 29.7% in 2018. Thus, most youths lack the means to cater for their basic necessities, be productive economically and self-sufficient. As a result, they have resorted to crime and other illegal activities to sustain themselves. Youths engage in all manners of crimes such as internet fraud, armed robbery, drug addiction and peddling, rape, prostitution, trafficking, kidnapping, insurgency, etc. This, no doubt portends that youth unemployment is a serious problem facing Nigeria in general and Kaduna state in particular.

In a bid to address youth unemployment and its attendant consequences, the Kaduna State government in collaboration with LGs initiated youth empowerment programs in 2011 with the aim of harnessing potentials of youths in the state and addressing the problem of unemployment. The programs which involved skills acquisition sought to empower youths with vocational and entrepreneurial skills in the area of hair making (stylist), fashion design (tailoring), digital photography, cosmetology, event planning and management, beads making, metal works (welding), brick laying, plumbing and carpentry. Against this backdrop, this research examines the extent to which the programs have empowered youths in the state with a particular focus on Kaduna South LGA. The research specifically attempts to find out how the programs have empowered youths to be productively engaged and self-reliant.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to determine the extent to which the empowerment programs introduced by the State government in collaboration with Kaduna South LG have provided employment to youths in the LGA. Specifically, it seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- I. To find out how the empowerment programs have enabled youths in the area to be productively engaged economically.
- II. To determine the extent to which the empowerment programs have facilitated youths in the area to be self-reliant.

Hypotheses of the Study

- I. H0: Empowerment programs introduced by Kaduna State government in collaboration with Kaduna South LG have not enabled youths in the area to be productively engaged economically.

- II. H0: Empowerment programs introduced by Kaduna State government in collaboration with Kaduna South LG have not aided youths in the area to be self-reliant.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Youth

The term youth is the time of life when an individual is young, especially the period between childhood and maturity of the early period of existence, growth or development. A youth generally refers to a time of life that is neither childhood nor adulthood but rather somewhere in between. Youth is an alternative word to the scientifically oriented adolescent and common terms of teen or teenage (Florence & Ekpungu, 2015). According to Jega (2012), youth is a special group of people with strong stamina and passion for realizing some goals and purpose. There is hardly any universally acceptable definition of youth, different countries define the word youth in relation to their objectives, conditions and existing realities on ground based on history, contemporary socio-economic and political issues as need to be addressed (Florence & Ekpungu, 2015).

Based on this, different parameters and variables are used in defining youth across countries. The UN considers individuals under the age group of 15-24 as youth. In Uganda, youth are persons between 12 to 30 years. In Nigeria, the National Youth Development Policy (2009) refers to all young persons of age 18 – 35 years as youth. This category of persons are seen as the most volatile and yet the most vulnerable segment of the population, socio-economically, emotionally and in other aspects. Youth share certain characteristics that distinguish them from other generation. These characteristics according to Florence and Ekpungu (2015), include impatience for change, zealotry, radicalism, rebellions, curiosity, hard work, ego and ambition.

Drawing from the above definitions, youths refers to persons within the category of late teens and early adulthood. That is, persons between 18 years and early 30s. The youths are seen as the engine and promoter of national development if their mind-sets are channeled in the right direction. In Nigeria, the youth constitute over one third of the country's 160 million population (NPC, 2006).

Concept of Empowerment

"Empowerment" has been used to represent a wide range of concepts and to describe a proliferation of outcomes. The term according to Malhorta et al (2002), has been used more often to advocate for certain types of policies and intervention strategies than to analyse them. Consequently, there are variances in the understanding of the term due to its widespread usage, thus meaning different things to different writers and organisations.

The term is generally believed to have derived its origin from the word "power". That is, "power to". This involves the ability or capacity to exercise control over a given

situation. Kabeer (2001) states, Empowerment should be conceived within the context of disempowerment and therefore refers to the processes by which those who have been denied the ability to make choices acquire such an ability. As stated by Kabeer, it is only those who have been disempowered that can be empowered.

To Narayan (2005), empowerment refers broadly to the expansion of choice and action to shape one's life. It implies control over resources and decisions. Empowerment is the expansion of assets and capabilities of poor people to participate in, negotiate with, influence, control, and hold accountable institutions that affect their lives. Empowerment relates to those who are powerless. The poor need power and a range of assets and capabilities to increase their well-being and security as well as their self-confidence, so they can negotiate with those more powerful (Petosky, Van Stelle, & De Jong, 1998).

Form the above definitions, it can be said that empowerment can simply be seen as a process that bestow power on people who are initially disempowered to live a life of their desire by expanding their assets and capabilities. It involves helping disempowered individuals to acquire skills, knowledge and assets in order to live a comfortable life. The essence of empowerment of any segment of the society is to ensure well-being of everyone so as to increase wealth and welfare of all living in that society.

Unemployment

The term 'unemployment' lacks a standard universal definition as various countries adopt definitions which suit their local priorities. However, all countries use the International Labour Organization (ILO) definition, or a variant of it to compute unemployment. According to ILO (1982), unemployment occurs when people within the age of 15-64 who have actively sought work within the past five weeks are without jobs. This means that only a person who is willing and available to work but can't find a job, can only be referred to as unemployed.

To Andrea, Piero, and Eliana (2004) the unemployed comprise those persons who were without work and immediately available to start work during the same period and who had actively looked for a job at some time during the preceding four weeks. The Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2018), sees unemployment as a proportion of those in the labour force (not in the entire economic active population, nor the entire Nigerian population) who were actively looking for work but could not find work for at least 20 hours during the reference period to the total currently active (labour force) population.

It can be concluded from the above definitions that unemployment refers to a situation where people between the ages of 15 and 64 (i.e. labour force) who are able and willing to work could not find job to do within a period under review.

Unemployment rate is a measure of the prevalence of unemployment and it is calculated as a % age by dividing the number of unemployed individuals by all individuals currently in the labour force. According to NBS (2018), unemployment rate is calculated by dividing the number of unemployed persons by labour force:

$$\text{Unemployment Rate} = 100 \times \frac{\text{Unemployed Population}}{\text{Labor Force Population}}$$

Unemployment in Nigeria

Unemployment is one of the most challenging problems being faced by the country today. It is no doubt a major problem ravaging Nigeria's population today and the youth are mostly affected by it. Unemployment rate has been on a consistent increase in the country over the years. Recent statistics has it on record that unemployment rose from 13.1% in the year 2000 to 19.7% in 2009 and rose again to 21.1% in 2010. In 2011, unemployment rate rose to 23.9% (NBS, 2012). In 2015, unemployment rate dropped to 9.9% but later rose to 13.9% in 2016 and rose again 18.8% in 2017. Presently, unemployment rate is put at 23.1% (NBS, 2018). Youth unemployment reached an all-time high of 29.7% in 2018 from 26.6% in the previous year. The Federal Government in 2008 acknowledged that about 80% of Nigeria's youth are either unemployed or underemployed (Daily Trust, November 2008). In a similar vein, the minister of youth development, Bolaji Abdullahi in 2011 reported that 42.2% of Nigeria's youth are out of job. Also, the National Youth Survey Report (2012) submitted that 54% of Nigerian youths were unemployed in 2012. The further stated that about 46,836 youths were recorded to have committed different types of crimes including drug abuse, fraud, theft, robbery, murder, rape, etc.

The above statistics show a worrisome level of unemployment in the country which if not addressed and speedily too could be a time bomb just waiting to explode. The alarming rate of crime in the country is not unconnected to the disturbing level of unemployment especially among the youth. Any effort, whether of the government, NGOs or CBOs aimed at providing employment for the teeming youths in the country must be accorded top priority and implemented religiously.

Youth Empowerment Programs

Jimba (2006), sees youth empowerment as involving diverse ways youths can be facilitated to cause changes in their life style. He maintained that youth empowerment means a way of inculcating into youths the spirit of transformation of ideas into creativeness. Youth empowerment can also be seen as a means of exposing youths to skills or training that makes them productive, which encompasses different ways youth can be exposed into different trades that may help them to engage in sustainable paid and self-employment (Idoko, 2014).

Ezeani (2012) refers to youth empowerment as an attitudinal, structure and cultural process whereby young people gain the ability, authority and agency to make decisions

and implement change in their own lives and lives of other people. Youth empowerment means creating and supporting the enabling conditions under which young people can act on their own behalf, on their own terms, rather than at the direction of others. These enabling conditions includes economics and social base, political will, adequate resource allocation and supportive legal and administrative frameworks, a stable environment of equality, peace and democracy and access to knowledge, information and skills and a positive value system (Undiyaundeye & Out, 2015).

Drawing from the above definitions, it can be said that youth empowerment involves any activity or program geared towards equipping youths with knowledge, skills, resources, etc. in order to enable them, to a large extent live a desired life (i.e. a life of their choice). It also include creating an enabling environment for youths to actualise their potentials.

Youth empowerment as espoused by the Kaduna State government in collaboration with Kaduna South LG entails equipping youths in the area with vocational and entrepreneurial skills such as hair making (stylist), fashion design (tailoring), digital photography, cosmetology, event planning and management, beads making, metal works (welding), brick laying, plumbing and carpentry in order to make them to be productively engaged and self-reliant so that they can provide for their basic necessities and live a desired life.

Empirical Studies

Ukoha, Osuji and Ibeagwa (2014) in their study on the influence of skills acquisition programs of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) on job creation in Abia state revealed a positive relationship between skills acquisition programs and job creation in the state. They submitted that the Agricultural Empowerment Program (AEP) and vocational skills development of the NDE have productively engaged youth graduates in the state. The study made use of questionnaires in generating data from a sample of 120 respondents, while secondary data were retrieved from textbooks, journals, and seminar as well as conference papers.

Kator and Adaigho (2015) study on appraisal of government youth empowerment programs through agriculture in Delta state submitted that the programs have yielded very little results in terms of empowering youths in the state to be productively engaged due to the criteria used in selecting beneficiaries and the inadequate training given to beneficiaries. The population for the study was drawn from youths across the state and multi-stage random sampling was employed to draw respondents from a sample of 275. Primary data were generated with the aid of questionnaires and interview while secondary data were extracted from internet materials, journals, textbooks and newspapers.

In another study on entrepreneurship development programs and youth employment

in Kano state by Dadango and Muhammad (2015), data generated majorly through administration of questionnaires revealed that relationship exist between the entrepreneurship programs and youth employment in the state. Nevertheless, the concluded that the EDPs cannot sustainably provide youths with means of livelihood due to problem of continuity, inadequate funding, lackadaisical attitude of youths towards the program and corruption.

Ndamu (2017) study on government empowerment programs and youth entrepreneurship in Adamawa state revealed that the government youth's empowerment programmes in Adamawa State have at different times supported youth's participation in entrepreneurial activities. Nevertheless, lack of involvement of social partners and stakeholders, corruption, policy inconsistency and poor governance were major challenges of the programs in the study area.

Studies reviewed above focused on different youths' empowerment programs in different states using various data collection instruments as well as measurement indicators. None focused on youths empowerment programs in Kaduna state, specifically the joint KDSG and Kaduna South LG youth empowerment programs. This study therefore represents an attempt to bridge this knowledge gap. Besides, this study adopts youths being productively engaged economically and self-sufficiency as measurement parameters for youth employment.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the survey research design, where data were generated from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were sourced through the administration of questionnaires and conduct of interviews. Secondary data on the other hand were derived from reports and official documents.

A total of 346 youths who are beneficiaries of the empowerment programs constituted population of the study. From this, a sample of 183 was drawn using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula. Interviews were conducted with officials of the council in order to assess the strength as well as challenges being faced in implementing the programs. Questionnaires on the other hand were randomly administered to youths who are beneficiaries of the programs in order to assess effect of the programs on unemployment reduction. To ensure validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was subjected to vetting by renowned scholars in the field of social welfare programs. Data generated from the questionnaires administered were processed and presented employing descriptive statistical tools such as frequency tables and percentage, while hypotheses were tested using Spearman rank correlation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Out of the one hundred and eighty- three (183) questionnaires administered to youths of Kaduna South LGA who have benefitted from the empowerment programs, one hundred and sixty-eight (168) were retrieved and found to be correctly filled and were

therefore used for analysis. This figure represents 91.8% of the total number of questionnaires administered.

Characteristics of Respondents

Analysis of demographic characteristics of respondents reveal a preponderance of males with 55.1% as against females with 44.9%. The age distribution shows that 24.4% were in the age bracket of 18-25 years; 39.7% fall within ages of 26 and 30; and 35.9% of them which constitute majority were within 31 – 35 years. In respect of their marital status, a preponderance of them constituting 80.4% were single, while 19.6% were married.

Their educational background reveals that 32.1% are holders of FLSC; 41% of them hold SSCE; 20.5% have ND/NCE; and 6.4% of them have HND/BSC. Evident here, is that not very many of the respondents have acquired higher education. The implication here is that non-graduates seems to have benefitted from the programs more, than graduates (Field survey, 2018).

Empowerment Programs and Youth Unemployment

The youth empowerment programs involved acquisition of vocational and entrepreneurial skills such as hair making, fashion design (tailoring), digital photography, cosmetology, event planning and management, beads making, metal works (welding), brick laying, plumbing and carpentry. Data generated revealed that 10.3% of the respondents benefitted from sewing and knitting; 12.8% were trained in the art of catering; 6.4% acquired carpentry skills; 12.8% were trained in the art of brick laying, tiles and interlocking; 7.7% learnt metal works (welding); 5.1% learnt plumbing; 9% acquired skills in digital photography; 11.5% were trained in the art of event management; 12.8% learnt soap and beads making; 3.8% were trained to make hair; and another 12.8% learnt computer and handset repairs. This shows that youths of the LGA were trained in various vocational skills. This corroborates the report of interview conducted with the Director of Education and Social Welfare Department of Kaduna South LG Council who happens to be the coordinator of the programs that beneficiaries were trained in several vocational skills.

Interview report further revealed that the duration of the programs ranged from 3 to 6 months. Brick laying, plumbing, catering, soap and bead making have a training duration of 3 months. While carpentry, metal works, event management, hair dressing and computer/handset repairs lasted for 6 months. Upon completion of training, beneficiaries were given starter packs (working tools), though about 17.5% of them complained of inadequacy of the starter pack. Others trained in digital photography, computing and metal works were made to go on attachment in some public and private organisations for a minimum of 6 months to acquire on-the-job training, after which some of the beneficiaries were retained by these organisations. (Field survey, 2018)

Programs' effect on youth unemployment

Table 1: I am now productively engaged as a result of the empowerment program?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	145	86.3
No	23	13.7
Total	168	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

As contained in table 1 above, majority of the respondents constituting 86.3% responded that they are currently engaged productively while 13.7% responded negatively to this. Based on these responses, it is evident that most of the beneficiaries are now involved in a productive activity.

Table 2: What is the nature of your productive engagement?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Self employed	105	62.8
Private firm	17	10.3
Public organisation	29	16.7
Others	17	10.3
Total	168	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

Regarding the nature of their productive engagement, 62.8% of them responded that they are self-employed; 10.3% work in private firms; 16.7% work in public organisations; and another 10.3% would not say. Perhaps these ones are not particularly engaged in any productive venture. Data contained here corroborate interview report that some of the beneficiaries of the programs who were attached to some public and private organisations ended up being permanently employed in the service of those organisations.

Table 3: Has your productive engagement translated in consistent earning of income?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	133	79.2
No	35	20.8
Total	168	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

As presented in table 3 above, a preponderance of the respondents constituting 79.2% responded in the affirmative while 20.8% responded negatively to this. It can be drawn from these responses that beneficiaries to some extent now have consistent income

flow as a result of their being productively engaged.

Table 4: To what extent has your income level risen?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Very much	28	16.7
Just much	65	38.7
Little	39	23.2
Indifferent	36	21.4
Total	168	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

As presented in table 4 above, 16.7% of the respondents opined that their income level has risen very much; 38.7% said just much; 23.2% of them responded 'little' and 21.4% were indifferent to this question. Despite the above half (55.4%) of the respondents who opined 'very much' and 'just much' to the extent of rise in income level, the about 40% who said 'little' or 'indifferent' is not a good omen for the program.

Table 5: To what extent can you now afford basic necessities such as food, clothing and shelter?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Very much	65	38.7
Just much	59	35.1
Little	28	16.7
Indifferent	16	9.5
Total	168	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

Regarding the extent they can now afford basic necessities, 38.7% of the respondents opined 'very much'; 35.1% responded 'just much'; 16.7% of them said 'little' and 9.5% were indifferent in their responses. Data contained here reveal that they (beneficiaries) can now afford basic needs as attested to by almost 90% of them, even though some 16.7% of them were of the opinion that the extent to which they can do this is little.

Table 6: Can you now afford to acquire household items?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Very much	31	18.5
Just much	42	25.0
Little	78	46.4
Indifferent	17	10.1
Total	168	100

Source: Field survey, 2018

As presented in table 6 above, 18.5% of the respondents opined 'very much'; 25.0% responded 'just much'; 46.4% of them said 'little' and 10.1% were indifferent in their

responses. Data here revealed that though a significant number of beneficiaries (40.5%) can now afford to acquire household property, very many of them (56.5%) lack the financial muscle to afford household items as shown in number of those who said 'just much' and 'little'.

Table 7: Challenges of the empowerment programs

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Inadequate funding	62	36.9
Shortage of qualified and experienced trainers	45	26.8
Lack of soft loans or credit facilities	33	19.6
Inadequate working tools (Starter pack)	28	16.7
Total	168	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Data contained in table 7 above represent respondents' opinion regarding challenges of the programs. 36.9% of them opined 'inadequate funding'; 26.8% opined that shortage of qualified and experienced trainers presented a major setback; 19.6% were of the opinion that lack of soft loans or credit facilities necessary to expand their enterprises was an issue; and 16.7% viewed inadequate provision of working materials (starter packs) as a major challenge. One can deduce from this data that inadequate funding, shortage of qualified and experienced trainers, lack of soft loans/credit facilities, and inadequate working tools in this order have constituted major setbacks of the empowerment programs.

Interview conducted with the coordinator (Director of Social Welfare) and a supervisor revealed that there was inadequate budgetary provision for the programs. This corroborated the opinion of the beneficiaries that the program was marred by inadequate finance. Nevertheless, both officials disagreed with beneficiaries on inadequate provision of working materials as they said it was adequately provided for. They also acknowledged that no plan was put in place to provide beneficiaries with soft loans to enable them expand their enterprises.

Test of Hypothesis

- i. *H₀: Empowerment programs introduced by KSDG in collaboration with Kaduna South LG have not enabled youths in the area to be productively engaged economically.*

Table 8: Result of Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient

<i>Spearman's rho</i>		<i>Empowerment programs of KSDG</i>	<i>Youths productive engagement</i>
<i>Empowerment programs of KSDG</i>	Correlation coefficient	0.05	.783*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	168	
<i>Youths productive engagement</i>	Correlation coefficient	.783*	0.05
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N		168

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS

Product

Spearman's correlation coefficient of 0.783 indicates a strong positive significant relationship between empowerment programs of the government and youth's productive engagement. Furthermore, the results show a high statistical significance of $p < 0.005$ thus it is safe to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the empowerment programs have significantly enabled youths in the LGA to be productively engaged economically as it has provided either self-employment or jobs in public and private organisations for them. This was corroborated by the findings of Ndamu (2017) who submitted that government youth's empowerment programmes in Adamawa State have at different times supported youth's participation in entrepreneurial activities. In further support of this, Ukoha and Ibeagwu (2014) in their study revealed a positive relationship between skills acquisition programs and job creation in Abia state. They submitted that the Agricultural Empowerment Program (AEP) and vocational skills development of the NDE have productively engaged youth graduates in the state. Nevertheless, the study of Kator and Adaigho (2015) revealed a near zero impact of government agriculture programs on youth empowerment in Delta state in terms of empowering youths to be productively engaged due to poor selection criteria and inadequacy of training given to beneficiaries.

- ii. *H₀: Empowerment programs introduced by KDSG in collaboration with Kaduna South LG have not aided youths in the area to be self-reliant.*

<i>Spearman's rho</i>		<i>Empowerment programs of KDSG</i>	<i>Youths self-reliance</i>
<i>Empowerment programs of KDSG</i>	Correlation coefficient	0.05	.645*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	168	
<i>Youths self-reliance</i>	Correlation coefficient	.645*	0.05
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N		168

Table 9: Result of Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS

Product

Correlation coefficient $r = 0.645$ reveals that a strong positive significant relationship exist between empowerment programs of the government and youth's self-reliance. Moreover, the tabulated value of 0.05 (5% level of significant) is less than p-value (.000), therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, it is safe to conclude that the empowerment programs have significantly empowered youths in the LGA to be self-reliant as their income level has visibly risen and they can now on their own to a large extent afford basic necessities of life such as food, clothing, etc. and acquire basic household items. The findings of Ndamu (2017) lend credence to this when it averred that government youth's empowerment programmes in Adamawa State have at different times supported youth's entrepreneurial participation which has resulted in youth being self-reliant. Ukoha, Osuji and Ibeagwa (2014) also corroborated this finding when they submitted that skills acquisition programs of the NDE in Abia state have productively engaged youth graduates in the state, thus leading to the youth being self-sufficient.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Youth empowerment programs are no longer seen as only a strategy to reduce unemployment and poverty as well as curbing crime but a means of promoting sustainable development. This study set out to examine the effect youths empowerment programs executed by Kaduna South LG Council have had on youths in the area in terms of empowering them to be productively engaged and being self-reliant. Data generated and analysed revealed that the programs have visibly empowered youths in the LGA to be productively engaged as well as being self-reliant which has translated in increased income as they can now afford basic necessities of life. However, the programs were marred with challenges of inadequate finance, shortage of qualified and experienced trainers/instructors, inadequate working tool,

etc. Conclusively, the effect of the program in terms of youth empowerment is commendable. It should be sustained and improved upon by addressing the identified challenges as it will no doubt address unemployment and curb youth restiveness.

REFERENCES

- Acemoglu, D., Johnson, S. & Robinson, J. A. (2001) Colonial Origin of Comparative Development. Africa' IDS Discussion Paper 383 (Brighton, Sussex: Institute of Development *African Studies*, 41/2 (2003) An Empirical Investigation. *American Economic Review*, Vol. 91, No. 5. p. 1369-1401.
- Andrea, B., Piero, C., & Eliana, V. (2004). Does the ILO definition capture all unemployment? Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.505.7688pdf>
- Awoko Newspaper*, PPRC now a Regulatory Body (2012), <<http://www.awoko>.
- Ayee, J.R. 2001. Reforming the African public sector: Retrospect and prospects. *African Journal of Political Science*, 6(1),1-41.
- Bless, C. & Higson-Smith, C. (2004). *Fundamentals of social research methods: An African perspective*. Lusaka: Juta Education.
- Conyers, D. (2007). Decentralization and service delivery: Lessons from Sub-Saharan Africa. *IDS Bulletin*, 38(1):2-19.
- Dandago, K. I. & Muhammad, Y. M. (2014). Entrepreneurship development programmes and facilitation of youth employment in Kano State, Nigeria *European Journal of Academic Research*, 2 (1), 17-30.
- Davis, T. 1990. Review and evaluation of Ghana's Civil Service Reform Programme, 1987-1989. Ottawa: World Bank Consultant's Report.
- Kator P. E. & Adaigho. P. (2015). An appraisal of governments youth empowerment programme through agriculture: The need for a new approach. *Advances in Crop Science and Technology*, 4 (1)
- Ndamu, R. K. (2017). Impact assessment of government empowerment programmes on youths participation in entrepreneurial activities in Adamawa state-Nigeria: 2000-2015. *International Journal of Development Strategies in Humanities, Management and Social Sciences (IJDSHMSS)*, 7(3), 81 – 93.
- Petoskey, E. L, Van Stelle, K.R. & De Jong, J. A. (1998). Prevention through empowerment in a native American community. *Drug & society*,12(1-2),147-162.
- Ukoha, I. I, Osuji, M. N, Osuji, E. E. & Ibeagwa. O. P. (2014). Analysis of the influence of

the skills acquisition programs of the national directorate of employment on job creation in Abia State. *Report and Opinion*, 6(3), 45-50.